

Media Advertising and Consumers' Buying Behavior in Banking Industry

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Abstract:- This study looked at the impact of media advertising on consumers' buying behavior in the banking sector—specifically, the case of Anbesa Bank. Media Advertising parameters which are broadcast media advertisement, Print media advertisement, outdoor media advertisement and Covert advertisement identified as the independent variables were adopted from [1], the dependent variable was determined to reflect consumer buying behavior. The research design used in the study was explanatory. Using a simple random sampling technique, 260 Anbesa Bank clients in Addis Ababa city provided the study's data. Structured questionnaires were utilized to collect pertinent data and SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) software was used to analyze the data. Descriptive, correlational and regression analysis approaches are employed to display the data. The study conclusion demonstrated that all forms of media advertising have a positive influence on consumers' purchasing decisions.

Keywords:- Broad Cast Media Advertisement, Print Media Advertisement, Outdoor Media Advertisement, Covert Media Advertisement And Consumers' Buying Behavior

I. INTRODUCTION

One element of the promotional mix is advertising, which is used to spread knowledge about goods and services in order to persuade consumers to make purchases. Advertising is the most effective marketing tool since it has the most mental effects on viewers [2]. Since early civilization, informal advertising has existed. Important businesses set themselves apart from rivals by producing stronger, amusing and imaginative commercials that can influence consumers' purchasing decisions as well as by sponsoring various events. Any production, manufacturing or service activity's goal is to enhance users' awareness and persuasion through various promotional activities, primarily advertising, leading to purchases and consumption. As a result, whatever good or service is created must effectively meet consumer wants. When the utility of the customer's money equals the usefulness of the offer s/he received in exchange for the consumer's money the consumer is considered to be most satisfied [3].

The majority of businesses examine consumer behavior and finding the elements that improve consumers' behavior in specific situations, such as economic issues, is the main goal of consumer behavior analysis [4]. Consumer behavior analysis is a tool that advertisers may use to better understand

how consumers behave when making purchases. Standard hierarchy-of-effects models state that exposure to advertising leads to brand cognition and cognition about the advertisements, which in turn produces attitude toward the advertisements and brands and, ultimately, buy intent [5].

Due to their rapid expansion, advertisements have developed into a very profitable industry and have acquired the status of both a distinct field of study and an autonomous discipline. [6]. As a result, advertising is a crucial tool for businesses to promote their products and services while boosting revenue. It's critical for companies to assess if their media advertising is successfully marketing their goods or not.

❖ *Statement of the problem*

All marketers, including banks, interact with their target markets through advertising in today's cutthroat and unstable marketplace [7]. Advertising has no chance of influencing consumers' purchase behavior for their products or services if the communication and information in the advertisement are insufficient or irrelevant to catch their attention.

Advertising must be consistent enough to be accepted and have an impact on customers' purchasing decisions when compared to data that has already been processed and is kept in long-term storage [7].

The requirement to draw and keep customers in the banking sector becomes a unique topic in uncertain global financial markets. Advertising is one of the prospective tools enhancing the financial institutions' economic efficacy. Specifically, their "intangible" nature and the unbreakable link between the stability of the banking institution and the clients' trust establish the peculiarities of advertising bank products and services.

The quality of information provided to current and potential customers during a campaign to build the bank's reputation and increase awareness of its products and services as well as to achieve a specific economic outcome decided before and after the transmission of the advertising message is the measure of a bank's advertising effectiveness. [8].

However, it is challenging to assess and understand the effect of media advertising on the financial outcome that is gained whether due to advertising or due to other promotional activities. The majority of financial institutions and Anbesa Bank of Ethiopia in particular, do not place much focus on undertaking advertising effectiveness research on consumer

purchasing behavior, which is the driving force behind this study.

Therefore, the purpose of this study was to determine how much media advertising affects consumers' decisions to purchase banking services. It also sought to determine which media (broadcast, print, outdoor, or covert) has the greatest influence on consumer purchasing decisions.

❖ *Research Questions*

- What is the effect of Broadcast media advertising on consumer buying behavior?
- What is the effect of print media advertising on consumer buying behavior in the banking service?
- What is the effect of outdoor media advertising on consumers' buying behavior in banking service?
- What is the effect of covert media advertising on consumers' buying behavior in banking service?
- Which media advertising type is mostly influential on consumers' buying behavior in banking service?

❖ *Objective of the study*

General Objective of the Study

The general objective of the study is to evaluate media advertising effects on consumers' buying behavior in Anbesa bank.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Approach: *mixed research approach*

Research Design: *explanatory research design is being examined for the study*

Size of the population: *Customers of Anbesa International Bank with a population of 260 random customers were chosen as the population size for the study and 249 customers appropriately filled out the questionnaire and returned to the researcher.*

Area for Sampling: *the sample area was gathered from Addis Ababa City.*

Sampling Design: *A probability sampling design (simple random sampling) is used to undertake the study and to complete the structured questionnaire on voluntary basis.*

Data collection Technique: *Data from both primary and secondary sources*

Data Analysis Technique: The data analysis was made using descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics was used to summarize and present the data. Regarding inferential statistics, regression analysis was used to test the significance contribution of each independent variable to the dependent variable.

➤ *Reliability Analysis*

Reliability refers to the degree of the results consistency under the same conditions. Reliability test was conducted to ensure internal consistency of the research instrument and Cronbach's alpha is used to measure the internal consistency of the measurement items (Bryman and Bell, 2019).

Below, Table 1, shows the reliability statistics of the data collected is 0.788. This is seen as adequate and permitted, for the scale variables.

Cronbach's Alpha	Number of Items
0.788	18

Table 1: Reliability Statistics

Source: Own Survey, (2022)

Media advertising effect on consumers' buying behavior was analyzed using linear regression; part of the process involves checking to make sure that the data is suitable for regression analysis. Therefore, it follows the following diagnoses test.

➤ *Multi-Co linearity*

Multicollinearity refers to the correlation among the independent variables. Multi collinearity can be checked using the tolerance and variance inflation factors (VIF) which are the two Co linearity diagnostics factors.

Model	Colinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
1. (Constant)		
BROADCAST	0.758	1.319
PRINT	0.704	1.421
OUTDOOR	0.669	1.495
COVERT	0.751	1.332

Table 2:- Co linearity Statistics

Source: Own Survey, (2022)

[9] describe Tolerance as an indicator that shows how much of the variability of a given independent variable is not explained by the model's other independent variables. It is calculated for each variable. If this value is very small (less than 0.10), it indicates that the multiple correlation with other variables is very high, suggesting the possibility of multi collinearity. The above items are all greater than 0.1 which implies that there is no multi collinairity or overlap between the independent variables.

As indicated by [9] Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) which calculates the influence of correlations among independent variables on the precision of regression estimates. The VIF factor should not exceed 10, and should ideally be close to one. As per the above table for all independent variables VIF value is less than 10 and literally closer to one, which implies there, is no multi collinearity problem. a correlation coefficient of less than 0.9 does not always indicate a major problem with multicollinearity. As a result, the above table quantity indicates that there is no multicolonarity issue.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The model summary in the Table, reports the strength of relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable. R is a Pearson correlation between predicted values and actual values of dependent variable, with a value of 0.919, which is a very high value. R² is multiple correlation coefficients that represent the amount of variance

of dependent variable explained by the combination of four independent variables. According to [10], the R square above 0.6 is accepted, conventionally. In this study, the R square resulted is 0.845, which shows the model is so fit, and then it is highly accepted.

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square		Std. Error of the Estimate	
0.919 ^a	0.845	0.819		0.28498	
ANOVA	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	7.973	39	2.658	102.724	0.000 ^b
Residual	1.462	206	0.81		
Total	9.435	245			

Table 3:- Regression model and analysis of variance by ANOVA

The ANOVA tells us whether the model, overall, results is a significantly good degree of prediction of the outcome variable [11]. F-ratio is the test statistic used to decide whether the model as a whole has statistically significant predictive capability, considering the number of variables needed to achieve it. Since, the significance result on the ANOVA table is 0.000 which is $p < 0.01$ and the regression mean square is greater than residual mean square with F value 102.724, the regression model fit to a very good degree of prediction.

Regression coefficients are estimates of the unknown population parameters and describe the relationship between a predictor variable and the response. In linear regression, coefficients are the values that multiply the predictor values. The following table shows the regression coefficients of the study.

Model	Un standardized Coefficients		Standard ized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	0.102	0.307		2.288	0.000
BROADCAST	0.615	0.114	0.469	3.625	0.002
PRINT	0.314	0.121	0.302	1.765	0.065
OUTDOOR	0.141	0.109	0.123	2.218	0.090
COVERT	0.111	0.098	0.894	1.127	0.080
Dependent Variable: CBB					

Table 4:- Regression Coefficients

From the table above we can say that B is 0.102, and this can be interpreted as meaning that if all the independent variables were to be zero, the model predicts that there can be 100% of consumers buying behavior. We can also read off the value of β from the table and this value represents the slope of the regression line. It is 0.615 for broadcast media and although this value is slope of the regression associated with a unit change in the outcome associated with a unit change in the predictor. Therefore, if broadcast media variable is increased by one unit, then the model predicts that 61.5% extra additional value on consumers buying behavior will be experienced.

The same is true for Print media (31.4%), Outdoor Media (14.1%) and Covert Media (11.1%), for which an increase in one unit of these respective variables can result in an increase in consumers buying behavior by the percentage shown. This impels that the media advertisement followed by an organization has a magnificent effect on Consumers Buying Behavior as their percentage indicated above.

From the regression analysis table of the study, it is observed that: **Broadcast media:** with p value of 0.002 is lower than 0.05: this implies that Broadcast media have a significant effect on Consumers Buying Behavior. For **Print Media:** it has a p value 0.065 which is greater than 0.05; this implies that, again, Print Media Ads has a significant effect on Consumers Buying Behavior. **Outdoor Media:** with p value of 0.09, which is greater than 0.05, this implies that Outdoor Media has significant effect on Consumers Buying Behavior. And for **Cover Media:** it has a p value 0.08, which is greater than 0.05, this implies that Covert Media has also significant effect on Consumers Buying Behavior.

The results of the study showed that all types of media advertisement significant effect on Anbesa Bank.

As the research indicated, above all dimensions, Broadcast media has a very strong and significant relationship with Consumers Buying Behavior which means customers of Anbesa Bank gives more emphasis on advertisements on television, radio, and internet. Therefore, Anbesa Bank marketing team is recommended to utilize and focus on advertisements on broadcast media Next to broadcast media, print media advertisement have also a strong effect on Consumers Buying Behavior in the case of Anbesa Bank Ethiopia. So It is recommended that managers/leaders at Anbesa Bank. To use print media ads as printed ads especially news papers could reach a wide range of target customers so marketing team in Anbesa Bank. It is recommended to use alternative and new ideas to boost advertisements on print Medias like news papers, magazine and brochures.

REFERENCES

- [1]. O'Guinn, Thomas C., Allen, Chris T., Semenik, Richard J.. (2018). Advertising and integrated brand promotion 3rd ed. (3rd).
- [2]. Katke, K., (2007). "The Impact of Television Advertising on child health & family spending international marketing conference on Marketing & Society <http://www.academia.edu>.
- [3]. Nartey, G. K. (2010) *The effect of Advertising on Consumer Behavior: A Case of MTN Ghana*, pp. 10-11, Unpublished MA Thesis, Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology, Kumasi, Ghana
- [4]. Ayanwale, A.B. & Ayanbimipe, M.A., (2005). The influence of Advertising on Consumes Brand Preference. *Journal of Social Science*, 10(1), pp 9-16
- [5]. Mendelson , A. L & Bolls, P.D (2017) Emotional Effect of Advertising on Young Adults of Socio Economic Status. <http://www.academia.edu>
- [6]. Khan, M. A. (2006). *Consumer behavior and advertising management*. New Delhi: New Age International. 2009).
- [7]. Mittal, S. and Pachauri, K.K. (2013) 'A Comparative Analysis of Promotional Tools & Techniques Adopted For Retail Banking In Public Sector and Private Sector Banks', *Journal of Business Management & Social Sciences Research (JBM&SSR) Volume2, ISSN No: 2319 & 5614, No.2, Available at: www.borjournals.com, /Accessed16/12/2013/*.
- [8]. Shakho, D. A. V and Panasenko , A. A. (2012) „Evaluating Effectiveness of Bank Advertising in the Internet: Theory and Practice“, *World Applied Sciences Journal 18 (Special Issue of Economics): ISSN 1818-4952, PP. 83-90, IDOSI Publications, Moscow Region, Russia*
- [9]. Wooldridge, Jeffrey M., 1960-. (2012). *Introductory econometrics : a modern approach*. Mason, Ohio :South-Western Cengage Learning,
- [10]. George, D., & Mallery, P. (2019). *IBM SPSS Statistics 26 Step by Step: A Simple Guide and Reference* (16th ed.).
- [11]. Field, A. (2018) Reliability analysis. In: Field, A., Ed., *Discovering Statistics Using spss*. 2nd Edition, Sage, London, Chapter 15.